

LIETUVOS SPORTO UNIVERSITETO REKTORIUS

ĮSAKYMAS DĖL LYČIŲ LYGYBĖS PLANO TVIRTINIMO

2025 m. birželio 30 d. Nr. ISAK 140/ B
Kaunas

Atsižvelgdamas į Tarptautinių ryšių skyriaus vedėjos Irenos Čikotienės prašymą,
i. t. v. i. r. t. i. n. u. pagal Europos Komisijos „Erasmus+“ projekto „SUPPORTER Securing
Sports Education through Innovative and Inclusive Gender Equality Plans“ (Projekto Nr.
101094529) gaires parengtą Lyčių lygybės planą.

Rektorė

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Kopijos pateikiamos:

1. Tarptautinių ryšių skyriui,
2. Ekonomikos ir finansų skyriui,
3. Žinių ir inovacijų perdavimo departamentui

LITHUANIAN SPORTS UNIVERSITY
GENDER EQUALITY PLAN
2025-2030

Gender equality is a fundamental principle of human rights, a cornerstone of democratic society, and a prerequisite for a sustainable, innovative, and competitive environment in higher education and research. As an institution dedicated to knowledge, critical thinking, and values, the University acknowledges its responsibility to ensure that every member of its community - regardless of gender, social status, age, ethnicity, sexual orientation, or other aspects of identity - has equal opportunities to participate in academic, research, administrative, and social life. In order to implement the principles of the European Charter for Researchers and the Magna Charter of European Universities, the Lithuanian Sports University (hereinafter - LSU or the University) organizes its activities by creating an open environment in which the individual differences, characteristics, potential and contribution of all employees and students are recognized and valued.

Every employee and student have the right to work and study in an environment that promotes respect for the dignity of every person. In order to foster and ensure the implementation of fundamental human rights enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Lithuania and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, the LSU Equal Opportunities Policy and its implementation procedure were approved in 2018. In 2021, the Lithuanian Sports University Code of Academic Ethics and the Lithuanian Sports University Description of Prevention and Case Investigation of Harassment, Sexual Harassment or Harassment were approved. The LSU Ethics Committee is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the Equal Opportunities and Diversity and Violence Prevention Policy at the University, investigating reports of University employees and students about violations of equal opportunities or harassment, consulting community members on equal opportunities issues and violations of equal opportunities. In 2021, The LSU Psychological Well-being Committee was established, which is responsible for effectively solving psychosocial problems and strengthening the mental health of students, lecturers and other university employees, creating a climate conducive to psychological well-being at the university, and carrying out practical, research and educational activities related to strengthening mental health. Therefore, LSU is committed to creating an open, inclusive, and safe environment for all members of its community by actively addressing systemic barriers, raising awareness of gender stereotypes, and ensuring the implementation of equal opportunity policies at all institutional levels. The Gender Equality Plan serves not only as a strategic document but also as a practical framework guiding the University's efforts to strengthen inclusiveness, transparency, and institutional awareness on gender equality.

A gender Equality Plan (GEP) - is an organization's action plan that sets out goals and priorities in the areas of equal opportunities, diversity and inclusion, provides specific measures and achieves desired results. The LSU GEP was prepared in accordance with the laws, policies and programmes of the Republic of Lithuania and international institutions: the Law on Equal Opportunities of the Republic of Lithuania; the National Programme on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men for 2021–2023; the Ministry of Education, Science and Sports of the Republic of Lithuania has prepared a document "Recommendations for ensuring equal opportunities for men and women in Lithuanian research and study institutions" and recommendations of the Lithuanian Equal Opportunities Ombudsman; the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE); accordance with article 20 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, the Council of Europe Directives (2000/43/EC, 2000/78/EC, 2014/54/EU, 92/85/EEC, 96/97/EC, 2006/54/EC).

The University, in order to ensure gender equality and promote an inclusive and innovative academic environment, actively implements these principles through various strategies and activities. One of the key commitments in this area is participation in the SUPPORTER (SecUring sPORTs Education through innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans) project for the period 2023-2025. During the SUPPORTER project activities and trainings participants obtained a lot of practical and theoretical

knowledge as well as received the strategical background for developing the GEP for sport community. Finally, the University committed to develop a Gender Equality Plan and ensure its implementation. The GEP will be meant for sport community – students, academic and administrative staff as well as in close cooperation with stakeholders as sport clubs, federations, associations, students union. In implementing this plan, the University is based on the following key principles:

- Ensuring equal opportunities – promoting equal access to academic and athletic resources and professional development opportunities.
- Awareness raising – training and seminars on gender equality and gender-based violence are organized to build understanding and change stereotypical attitudes.
- Monitoring and evaluation – regular research and surveys are conducted to monitor the current situation and progress of psychological well-being and psychosocial risk factors in the university community, as well as to assess the effectiveness of the GEP and plan further steps.

The goals, activities, and measures set out in this GEP are primarily the responsibility of the LSU. In order to ensure the effective implementation of the GEP and to contribute meaningfully to the development of gender equality strategies, it is essential to foster sustainable cooperation with relevant stakeholders beyond the University, while also clearly delineating roles and responsibilities within the institution itself.

Internal responsible units	External institutions and responsible representatives
Senate	Ministry of Education, Science and Sports of the Republic of Lithuania – <i>for contribution to the preparation of reports, analyses and policies in the field of gender equality</i>
Council	Lithuanian Equal Opportunities Ombudsman – <i>for contribution to the preparation of reports, analyses and policies in the field of gender equality</i>
Rector	National Sports Agency
Vice-Rectors (for Study, Research, Infrastructure)	The National Olympic Committee of Lithuania (LNOC)
Ethics Commission	Sports schools and canterers
Psychological Wellbeing Committee	Sports associations
Marketing and Communications Department	FU teachers
Students' Union	Athletes
Researchers, scientists	Sports managers
Teachers	Couches
Human Resources and Management Division	Sports federations
Knowledge and Innovation Relay Division	Athletes, parents
Department of Marketing and Communications	
Department of Physical and Social Education	

The main goal of LSU GEP is - to promote a common institutional understanding of gender equality goals and ensure the sustainability of related results at the Lithuanian Sports University, in line with national and European gender equality policies, with particular attention to the areas of sport, physical education and sports science.

To achieve this goal, the following **objectives** are set:

- To strengthen the institutional framework for gender equality by systematically integrating the gender dimension into the University's strategic planning, governance documents, and development policies (impactful).
- To foster an inclusive, equality-oriented organizational culture by enhancing internal and external communication and promoting active cooperation with social partners and the wider community (inclusive).
- To promote equal career opportunities and improve gender balance in decision-making and leadership positions, while increasing awareness of gender equality issues and enhancing the efficiency of gender-related data collection and analysis (innovative).
- To incorporate gender and broader diversity perspectives into teaching, learning, and research processes, thereby ensuring that study programmes and research activities reflect principles of equity, inclusion, and social responsibility (intersectionality).

SUMMARY OF LSU 2025-2030 GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

LSU 2025-2030 Gender Equality Plan is the foundation for the University's goal to promote gender equality, diversity, and ensure violence prevention. This Gender Equality Plan (GEP) aims to promote gender equality and combat gender-based violence (GBV) and diversity at the University including all sport community – students, staff and social partners. The plan is designed with inclusion, innovation, intersectionality, and impact in mind, ensuring that all students, staff, and athletes can thrive in a safe and just environment. The plan includes activities focused on work-life balance, organizational development, organizational culture, hiring and promotion, as well as gender representation in leadership positions and participation in decision-making governing bodies.

EDUCATION OF EMPLOYEES, STUDENTS, AND SPORTS COMMUNITY

In order to promote awareness of gender equality and diversity in the University and the sports community and ensure the prevention of violence and discrimination (taking into account all marginalized groups, including LGBTQ+ individuals and persons with disabilities), it is important to regularly organize seminars, trainings and information campaigns for students, employees and coaches, which would create conditions for developing a tolerant organizational culture and creating traditions that promote it. Targeted education of members of the University and sports community that strengthens competencies and shapes their behaviour on relevant topics is one of the most important cross-sectoral elements of the LSU 2025-2030 Gender Equality Plan.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Specific resources have been allocated for the successful implementation of the LSU 2025-2030 Gender Equality Plan. These resources are intended for the development of training programs, as well as for ensuring support for leaders, staff and students. The Psychological Wellbeing Committee, the Marketing and Communications Department, the Ethics Committee and the Student Association dedicate their working time to monitoring the progress of the implementation of the LSU 2025-2030 Gender Equality Plan and its implementation.

CONTINUOUS DATA COLLECTION AND MONITORING

LSU collects and monitors gender-disaggregated data on staff and students by major study levels (more consistent data disclosure is needed). The Psychological Wellbeing Committee collects data on issues related to gender equality and gender-based violence and other diversity. The data is included in the University's annual report and is also provided to the University community, highlighting key figures and issues related to gender equality and diversity.

Statistical data

National

In 2024, Lithuania's Gender Equality Index reached 65.8 out of 100 reflecting a modest improvement of 1.7 points compared to previous years. This result placed Lithuania 16th among EU Member States. Despite the progress, Lithuania still lags behind the EU average. (lygybe.lt). In Lithuania, employment rates between men and women differ, with women often facing greater challenges in balancing professional and personal life. The gender pay gap remains significant. (osp.stat.gov.lt). 77% of victims of domestic violence are women, while 84% of suspects are men (lygiadieniai.lt).

Sports field. In Lithuania, women make up 35% of all athletes. The share of female athletes under 18 is higher – 37%, and over 18 years – 30%. This shows that in younger age groups, girls are more involved in sports. Of the 34 Olympic sports federations in Lithuania, only three – table tennis, figure skating and climbing – have women as presidents. Among the federations' vice-presidents, out of 54, only 6 are women. Among registered coaches in Lithuania, women make up 29%, but their share is higher at the elite level – 36%. In certain sports, such as figure skating (88%) and field hockey (60%), the proportion of female coaches is particularly high. However, in sailing and rugby, there are no female coaches at all, and in ice hockey, men account for 98% of all coaches. Only 12 sports federations in Lithuania have written rules and action plans on how to prevent and combat gender-based violence. Only 4 federations have integrated monitoring and evaluation mechanisms in this area. 15 federations have included the issue of gender equality in their long-term plans, and 4 federations (basketball, football, archery and taekwondo) have drawn up written statutes to achieve this goal (LNOC).

LSU

Figure 1. LSU Gender Data (Students, 2023 y) **Figure 2.** LSU Gender Data (Academic and administrative stafs, 2023 y)

Figure 3. LSU Gender Data (Academic staff, 2024 y) **Figure 4.** LSU Gender Data (Academic staff, 2024 y)

LSU 2025-2030 GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

The Gender Equality Plan is aiming to include **innovative, impactful, inclusive and intersectional points** adjusted to the peculiarities of sports higher education institutions. The SUPPORTER project has supported the University with capacity building, mutual learning, and monitoring and mentoring schemes. Some tools as learning diaries, roadmaps, trainings were developed through all project period by LSU project team, all these means helped to develop a long-lasting Gender Equality Plan for Lithuanian Sports University community.

Impactful action: Strengthen gender equality policies by integrating the gender equality dimension into strategic documents

Activity	Target audience	Indicators	Responsible departments and Implementation
Integrate a gender equality and gender-based violence (GBV) dimensions into LSU Strategy, update the Code of Ethics and other strategic processes	University community	Prepared and updated implementation documents	LSU Senate, Council, Rector, Vice-Rectors, Ethics Commission, Human Resources and Management Division SUPPORTER project group 2026 - 2030
Ensure the implementation of the Equal Opportunities and Gender Equality Plan 2025-2030	University community	Monitoring of the implementation of strategic documents is carried out	LSU Senate, Vice-Rectors, Ethics Commission, Psychological Wellbeing Committee SUPPORTER project group. 2025 - 2030

Inclusive action: Creating an inclusive and equality-oriented organizational culture through the university's internal and external communication and cooperation with social partners

Activity	Target audience	Indicators	Responsible departments and Implementation
Initiating internal communication initiatives to promote gender equality, diversity and GBV prevention (including in sports)	University community Sports community (LNOC, National Sports Agency, sports federations, sports schools etc.)	Number of training, communication or events highlighting gender aspects in scientific research, showing role models, etc., cycle	Marketing and Communications Department Psychological Wellbeing Committee 2025 - 2030

Strengthen cooperation with national and international social partners, working in the field of human rights, equal opportunities, gender equality and GBV in sports	Sports community (LNOC, National Sports Agency, sports federations, sports schools etc.) Universities	Number of contracts, joint events, projects	Marketing and Communication Department Students' Union Researchers, scientists' Non-academic staff 2025 - 2030
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Innovative action: Increase equal career opportunities and improve gender balance in leadership positions, raise awareness and make information data collection more efficient

Activity	Target audience	Indicators	Responsible departments and Implementation
Encouraging suitably qualified women and men to equally seek leadership positions and participate in decision-making bodies	University community	Similar number of women and men holding leadership positions and representing decision-making bodies of the University	LSU Senate, Vice-Rectors, Human Resources and Management Division SUPPORTER project group Ongoing activities 2025 - 2030
Create and expand an information section on the LSU website dedicated to knowledge related to gender equality, GBV and other diversity in sports	University community Sports community Everyone visiting the website	Created section on the LSU website	Psychological Wellbeing Committee Information Technology Department 2025 - 2030
Developing methods will help involving more students and university staff in questionnaires, active participation in seminars and workshops	University community	Prepared methods A larger number of community members (especially students) responded to the questionnaire	Psychological Wellbeing Committee Students' Union ESN Tutors 2025 - 2026
Monitor gender distribution at all levels of the university – from study programs and student admissions to academic, administrative and leadership positions	University community	Consistent monitoring of gender equality indicators and periodic provision of information to the university community	Human Resources and Management Division Psychological Wellbeing Committee Information Technology Department 2025 - 2030

Intersectionality action: Integrate gender and diversity dimensions into studies and research

Activity	Target audience	Indicators	Responsible departments and Implementation
Encourage teachers and researchers to integrate the gender, GBV, religion, ethnicity, age, socio-economic status and disability dimension into study subjects and programs, research, knowledge and technology transfer	Students Teachers Researchers	Increased number of study subjects, thematic and research (e.g. bachelor or master thesis) that reflect gender, GBV and diversity issues Increased number of thematic in study subjects and research (for example bachelor or master thesis) that reflect gender and diversity issues	Department of Studies Vice-Rector for Studies Vice-Rector for Research Department of Physical and Social Education Lecturers Researchers 2025 - 2030
Conduct training and consultations related to gender, GBV, religion, ethnicity, age, socio-economic status and disability issues in sport for lecturers, researchers, PE teachers, coaches, sports managers	Teachers Researchers PE teachers Coaches Sports managers	Increased number of trainings and consultations	Vice-Rector for Studies Projects Department Knowledge and Innovation Relay Division Department of Marketing and Communications Psychological Wellbeing Committee 2025 - 2030

Useful links:

SUPPORTER (SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans)

<https://www.supporter-project.eu/>

European Commission - Gender equality strategy

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en

European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)

https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/institutions-and-bodies/search-all-eu-institutions-and-bodies/european-institute-gender-equality-eige_en

EU publications - Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

EU publications - Impact of gender equality plans across the European research area

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/906fcb4a-e504-11ef-bc1c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Europos lyčių lygybės institutas (EIGE)

<https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/institutions-and-bodies/search-all-eu-institutions-and-bodies/european-institute-gender-equality-eige> It

LR Lygių galimybių įstatymas

<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.222522>

Lygių galimybių kontrolieriaus tarnyba

<https://lygybe.lt/>

Moterų ir vyrų lygių galimybių įgyvendinimo 2021–2023 m. nacionalinė programa

<https://e-seimasx.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/7a085132a0df11eda06e9a4a8dd92fc1?jfwid=-7j2b4ao3r>

Lietuvos olimpinis komitetas. Lyčių lygybė sporte

<https://ltok.lt/lyciu-lygybe-sporte>